

Tombs at Ketef Hinnom

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This is an elite mortuary complex located on the western shoulder of the Hinnom Valley in Jerusalem. The site was excavated by the Institute of Archaeology of Tel Aviv University for five seasons (1975, 1979, 1980, 1988 and 1989). Excavations focused upon seven rock-cut tombs which were created in the late Iron Age but continued in use through the late Hellenistic period. The tomb complex closely resembles other elite tombs such as those at St. Etienne in Jerusalem dating to the late Iron Age. One particular tomb complex and its repository (Cave 24, Chamber 25) yielded over a thousand grave items, including two inscribed amulets containing versions of the biblical Priestly Blessing (Numbers 6:24-26) and other formula known from the biblical texts (Deut. 7:9; Neh. 1:5; Dan. 9:4). These amulets were manufactured from thin sheets of silver and rolled into scrolls for use as jewelry. Their inscriptions appear on the interiors of the tiny metal scrolls and likely contained the names of their wearers.

Date Range: 800 BCE - 200 BCE

Region: Ketef Hinnom

Region tags: Middle East, Israel, Palestine, Judah, Israel in the Second Temple period

The cave tombs of Ketef Hinnom outside Jerusalem.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: G. Barkay, "The Priestly Benediction on Silver Plaques from Ketef Hinnom in Jerusalem." *Tel Aviv* 19 (1992): 139-92.
- Source 2: G. Barkay, A. G. Vaughn, M. J. Lundberg, B. Zuckerman, "The Amulets from Ketef Hinnom: A New Edition and Evaluation." *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 334 (2004): 41-71.
- Source 3: J. Smoak, *The Priestly Blessing in Inscription and Scripture: The Early History of Numbers 6:24-26* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2015).

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

— Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1975, 1979, 1980, 1988 and 1989

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Ketef Hinnom, Institute of Archaeology of Tel Aviv University

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Cave

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Rock escarpment

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Other [specify]: Cemetery

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– I don't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– I don't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– I don't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– I don't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: burial

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– I don't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– I don't know

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– I don't know

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to the elements:

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– I don't know

↳ Other intensive (time/resources expended) treatment [Specify]:

– Other [specify]: bench for preparation of corpse

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Coins, pottery, statuettes, and other objects

↳ Other

– Yes [specify]: Complete pottery, Assyrian type bathtub clay coffin, jewelry, glass objects, stone spindle whorl, beads, shells, tools, arrowheads, Greek coin, Hebrew inscriptions

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Yes

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: no

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– I don't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– I don't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 0

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: do not know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– I don't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– I don't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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Reference: Tombs at Ketef Hinnom, Quick, Laura. *Dress, Adornment, and the Body in the Hebrew Bible*. Oxford University Press, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198856818.001.0001>.

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Reference: Tombs at Ketef Hinnom, Suriano, Matthew. *Writing and the Tomb*. Oxford University Press, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780190844738.003.0004>.